

at 14% moisture content was 86-92%.

The seeds were stored in paper bags, with the top folded twice and clipped, on wooden shelves Nov 1984-May 1987. Average and maximum and minimum room temperatures and relative humidity during storage are given in Table 1. A 300-seed sample was randomly drawn for each variety in May 1987; one-half of each sample was dehulled. The seeds were put in petri dishes on moist filter paper at room temperature for germination, with 50 seeds constituting a replication.

In general, germination percentage dropped over 30 mo storage. However, there was not much variation in germination between hulled and dehulled seeds. The varieties could be grouped into 3 classes on the basis of germination percentage: no germination, less than 25% germination, and more than 25% germination (Table 2).

Germination ranged from 0 (Salumpikit, Dourado Precoce) to 40% (IR10004-1-1-2), suggesting genetical control for this trait.

These genotypic differences could be used to save the effort of growing out

Table 2. Germination of 24 rice varieties before and after storage. Hazaribag, India.

Variety	Initial germination (%)	Germination (%) after 30 mo	
		Hulled grain	Dehulled grain
IR12919-24-1-8	88	39	38
IR10004-1-1-2	90	40	35
IR27095-20-3	92	35	37
IR6023-10-1-1	92	18	20
IR10120-7-2-1-4	92	22	16
Kinandang Patong	86	20	16
IAC47	89	12	10
IR54	92	8	7
IRAT13	87	7	6
IR38	90	6	6
AC540	90	6	6
H105	87	4	4
IRAT110	88	3	2
CR125-12-8	92	0	0
IAC25	92	0	0
IR34	92	0	0
IRAT109	92	0	0
Kulu	91	0	0
Ngoba	90	0	0
IRAT116	90	0	0
IRAT10	88	0	0
IAC165	88	0	0
Salumpikit	86	0	0
Dourado Precoce	86	0	0

entire germplasm collections every year. Varieties showing more than 25% germination could be stored for 2 yr and regenerated the third year. Genotypes

like IR12979-24-1-8, IR27095-20-3, and IR10004-1-1-2 could be used as donors for long storage life. □

Genetics

Isozyme polymorphism for *Est-2* locus observed at rice vegetative and reproductive phases

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We analyzed IR36 and IR64 (indicas) and Taichung 65 (japonica) for isozyme polymorphism at vegetative and reproductive phases using three isozyme loci (*Est-2*, *Amp-3*, and *Pgi-2*). The analysis was to determine the allelic constitution for various isozyme loci used to study linkage relationships with the wide compatibility gene (*Sⁿ*). Isozyme polymorphism in the three cultivars is presented in the table.

Taichung 65 showed differential behavior of *Est-2* alleles at the vegetative

(*Est-2⁰*) and reproductive phases (*Est-2²*). Recently, differential behavior of *Est-2* alleles was reported in cold-tolerant rices. Cultivars possessing *Est-2⁰* allele were more tolerant than those with *Est-2¹* and *Est-2²*. Taichung 65 is known to show cold tolerance at the vegetative phase, but susceptibility at the reproductive phase.

This raises the question whether the isozyme polymorphism for *Est-2* locus

Isozyme polymorphism for 3 isozyme loci -- *Amp-3*, *Est-2*, and *Pgi-2* -- at vegetative and reproductive phases.^a IRRI, 1988.

Cultivar	Isozyme pattern					
	<i>Amp-3</i>		<i>Est-2</i>		<i>Pgi-2</i>	
	V	R	V	R	V	R
IR36	3 ¹	3 ¹	2 ²	2 ²	2 ²	2 ²
IR64	3 ¹	3 ¹	2 ²	2 ²	2 ²	2 ²
Taichung 65	3 ¹	3 ¹	2 ⁰	2 ²	2 ¹	2 ¹

^aV = at vegetative phase, R = at reproductive phase.

observed at vegetative and reproductive phases in Taichung 65 and other rice cultivars can be related to their cold tolerance at the two growth stages. □

Inheritance of high density grain in rice

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The parents, F₁, and F₂ of a cross of diverse parents IR30 and IR32385-37-3-3-3 (high density grain index [HDI] 56% and 29%, respectively) were grown in the greenhouse during 1987 wet season to study inheritance of this trait.

HDI was calculated by dividing the number of high density grains (specific gravity >1.20) by spikelets per panicle on primary (Pb) and secondary (Sb) branches (50 panicles of each parent and